

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Enviromental ImpactTs Hybrid storage forR Concentration Solar Technologies
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	EITHER-CST
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS- The Cyprus Institute
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Thermal Storage, Batteries, Micro-Grid, annual modelling, LCA
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	22/06/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	30/06/2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	22/06/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	29/06/2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	3 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	2 days weekend
Number of days using the RI	6 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	1 user
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The main objective from EITHER CST project was the definition of the life cycle assessment (LCA) of the current storage systems. For this purpose, this study uses a framework that combines the LCA evaluation of two storage systems (electro-chemical and thermal storage) by using SimaPro Power* software, Ecoinvent database, and the IMPACT 2002+ method with a Cradle-to-Gate (CtG) approach. For this project, one visit to the Cyprus Institute has been programed to get familiar with the PROTEAS site and collect data. The collaboration started with the information sharing about the current related facilities at PROTEAS, as built-in terms of micro-grid power and storage</p>	

components. The project's visit took place from 22nd -30th June 2023. PROTEAS provided support and the required information to the User from Corvinus University of Budapest, who was in charge of the impact's evaluation for the storage technologies, and Clement Tissot (Intern from the Laboratoire de Genie Chimique of Toulouse (France) shared experiences in developing the LCA for other technologies.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

1. Problem definition.

This step was defined in advance. In this research project two storage systems have been defined as case studies: (1) electro-chemical storage (lead-acid batteries): used to store electricity generated by a wind turbine and a PV system. (2) thermal storage (molten salt tank): used to store thermal energy coming for CSP

2. Arrival to the Cyprus Institute.

The first day, an introduction about the Cyprus Institute was given and an office was assigned to me. The preparations for the visit to the PROTEAS site took place also the first day. The administrative requirements for me to have access to the site were completed. I was introduced to the institute's team members and interns, and I was invited to attend a conference about IPCC report and Climate Change.

3. Visits to the PROTEAS site (several visits) with the focus on the systems in the scope of the project.

4. Data collection.

Data was taken for the two storage technologies

a. First, a visit to the electro-chemical storage room took place. The lead-acid batteries were described and technical data about the model, brand, and capacity was taken.

b. Then, a visit to the molten salt tank room was done. The thermal storage system was described and technical data about the system was discussed but additional information was needed (dimensions, materials, etc.).

c. Technical drawings. Were provided by the engineering team at PROTEAS

d. Literature search. Additional search online was needed to find information about the lead-acid batteries, and in general about the energy systems

5. Tools and methods

a. The main objective from EITHER CST project was the definition of the life cycle assessment (LCA) of the current storage systems. Each storage system was analyzed separately.

b. LCA is viewed as a standardized, mature, systems-oriented analytical tool assessing potential impacts of products or services using a lifecycle perspective in accordance with guidance of ISO 14040 and 14044 standards (Kim et al., 2019). LCA involves the definition of goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation (Figure below). Software and tools: SimaPro Power software Ecoinvent database, and the IMPACT 2002+ method with a Cradle-to-Gate (CtG) approach.

- c.
- d. Inventory development in Simapro using Ecolnvent

6. Results and data analysis.

Once the inventory was completed, two methodologies were tested for the life cycle inventory analysis (LCIA): RECIPE and IMPACT 2002+.

a. In summary, lead-acid batteries resulted in higher damage than the thermal storage for all the environmental damage categories (see next section for additional insights).

7. Report development (in Word using results from Simapro).

- a. Developed from 23 June to 10 July 2023
- b. Storage systems' description
- c. Results discussion: preliminary results for storage systems' environmental impact (LCA) are discussed
- d. Report review

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Note: A longer report was developed for the Cyprus Institute where the three strategies for quantifying the impacts are given, i.e., (1) LCA for lead batteries system, (2) LCA for the molten salt tank, and (3) comparison of both systems. Here we just present the latest due to its relevance.

The results of the environmental impacts generated by each of the storage facilities are expressed here based on the chosen functional unit, 1 kWh of net delivered electricity (functional unit: per kWh delivered), also called useful kWh. The formulas used for the calculation of the useful kWh (actual capacity) are given in equation 1 and 2 and the results are displayed in Table 1

$$Actual\ Capacity_{Lead-Acid} = (Full\ Cap.) (Discharging\ Eff.) (Charging\ Eff.) (Max.\ depletion) \dots (1)$$

$$Actual\ Capacity_{MoltenSalt} = (Mass) (Specific\ Cap.) (\Delta Temp) (Turbine\ Eff.) \dots (2)$$

Lead-Acid Battery	Qty	Unit
Mass/battery	58,4	kg
Full capacity/battery	1,98	kWh
Charging efficiency	95%	
Discharging efficiency	90%	
Maximum depletion	20% ¹	
Actual battery capacity	0,33858	useful kWh/battery (around 3 batteries are needed to deliver 1 kWh)
	0,005797603	kWh/kg
Actual battery capacity (all batteries)	16,9	useful kWh (system)
Molten salts (tank)	Qty	Unit
Mass (only salt mixture)	13778	kg
Specific capacity	1530	J/kg C
Temperature (T _{max} -T _{min})	270	C
Discharging efficiency (Turbine efficiency)	10%	
Actual tank capacity	569169180	J
	158,1	useful kWh (system)

Table 1. Actual capacity calculation for lead-acid batteries and molten salt storage

Once common units are known, it is possible to treat the LCA results to compare electro-chemical vs thermal storage systems at PROTEAS

Table 2 summarized the results and for all the endpoint categories, higher damage is found for the lead-acid batteries. As a validation of the order of magnitude, the Global Warming has been taken as a reference

We found that for every kWh delivered (around 3 batteries are needed for that output - see Table 1), around 450 kg CO₂eq are produced. This number is comparable with the results found by (Yudhistira et al., 2022) in which 104-169 kg CO₂-eq are produced per kWh battery capacity (nominal) in this sense, since we are using actual and not nominal capacity, the results are similar (the maximum depletion of the analysed system is 20%). For the other categories we do not have a reference to compare results at this point.

Damage category	Lead-Acid batteries	Molten Salt tank	Unit (per useful kWh)
Human health	0,001509844	0,00052	DALY ²
Ecosystem quality	408,8346951	216,07134	PDF ⁺ m ₂ *yr
Climate change	448,510312	392,21116	kg CO ₂ eq
Resources	8269,905867	4502,15066	MJ primary

Table 2. IMPACT 2002+ damage for a functional unit of 1kWh from lead-acid and molten salt storage

When values are normalized, the midpoint different clearly display the bigger impact of lead-acid batteries in the environment compared to the thermal storage (Figure 1). When values are brought to 1kWh, the global warming impact is larger for batteries than for the molten salt tank. This example displays the importance of using a common functional unit to correctly identify main damage of comparable systems since in the individual analysis, it was displayed that for the damage categories, the molten salt tank had a bigger share in the Global Warming contribution (25% vs 13% for batteries). For this reason, the analysis of normalized data should be always interpreted based on the functional unit.

The damage categories are given in Figure 2. Lead-acid batteries result in higher damage than the thermal storage for Human Healthy (biggest damage), Resources, Climate change and Ecosystem quality.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

Although renewable energies are considered as green energy, intermittency is one of their main limitations. Cyprus has great solar potential and the PROTEAS site counts with CSP, Solar PV and Wind technologies to inject power into the grid. Two storage facilities are used to balance the load: electro-chemical and thermal storage (lead-acid batteries and the molten salt tank, respectively). The lifecycle assessment has been implemented for both storage systems in Simapro by using the Ecoinvent 3 database (Ecoinvent, 2023). In this report, only preliminary results are presented.

For the electro-chemical storage, the functional unit (FU) chosen was 1 lead-acid battery system (50 batteries). IMPACT 2002+ method has been selected to perform the entire analysis due to its application in other similar cases from the literature. For this technology higher values were found for Non-Carcinogens, Respiratory (organics and inorganics), Non-renewable energy, Global warming and Terrestrial ecotoxicity; and higher damage in Human Health (62%), followed by damage to Resources (16%), Climate change (13%), and Ecosystem quality (9%).

For the thermal storage, the FU was 1 molten salt tank from which 6 material had been identified and measured to perform the LCI based on the different layers or materials used in the tank: AISI 316L, ceramic wool, rock wool, aluminum, NaNO₃ (sodium nitrates), and KNO₃ (potassium nitrates). This material breakdown allowed to have a deeper level of analysis (compared to the lead-acid battery) because the impacts can be linked to each material. The IMPACT 2002+ reports the highest damage for the system for Human Health (46%) followed by Climate change (25%), Resources (19%), and Ecosystem quality (10%). The salt mixture (NaNO₃ and KNO₃) shows an important effect in all the midpoints but when talking about the damage their higher contribution goes to Climate change and Resource damages. Aluminum has a consistent share in the four damage categories while Steel is the material with the highest damage contribution to Ecosystem quality and Human health. Ceramic and rock wool resulted in a negligible damage.

However, to be able to have a comparison between the two storage systems, a first attempt to use a common unit was proposed by having an approximative calculation of 1 kWh of net delivered electricity. Results display higher damage for lead-acid storage in all the evaluated aspects being outstanding for human health damage in accordance with the individual results (Non-Carcinogens, Respiratory (organics and inorganics)). The negative effects of terrestrial ecotoxicity, non-renewable energy and global warming are also clearly higher when using lead-acid battery technology.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)
<p>1. Case study definition. It was necessary to be onsite to clearly define the scope of the study. Moreover, since there is also an intern working on the development of LCA for other systems, we could share ideas.</p> <p>2. Data collection. During the visit, we had access to the required information in terms of the technology and with regards to the materials inventory</p> <p>3. LCA for independent systems. This has been a challenge due to the short available time and also to the problems in accessing the software. However, due to a serious involvement from all the participants, the development of LCA for the both systems was successfully completed.</p> <p>4. Comparison of both technologies. This is an additional achievement, not part of the original plan, once the results of independent systems were found, the team at PROTEAS was interested in comparing the systems and a new functional unit was used to be able to contrast results from both systems. This analysis resulted in the most interesting outcomes from the project.</p> <p>5. Report development. The report has been developed from 23 June to 10 July 2023 and there is a short report that was developed for StoRIES but also a longer one for the continuation of the collaboration and as a baseline for the projected publication.</p> <p>6. Networking. After this visit, both parts expressed their intention to collaborate in the near future.</p>
Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)
<p>We had some limitations in running the LCA inventory and assessment due to the lack of license for Ecolnvent. For that reason, we needed to ask for support from an external partner. This is, however, not a problem from the Research Infrastructure (RI) nor the user because they don't have the Simapro license, and the user knew that in advance. In the original plan, a free software, OpenLCA, was projected as the software to be used but after several attempts we could not have access to the Ecolnvent database. For that reason, the Laboratory of Chemical Engineering from the University of Toulouse supported us in providing data from the databases</p>
Intended publications
<p>We plan to submit a paper with the results of this project in an international journal before the end of 2023.</p>
Data management
<p>All the data for this project was stored in the internal cloud from the Cyprus Institute (for more details please contact PROTEAS)</p>
Conclusions / additional comments
<p>Thank you so much for this fantastic and productive opportunity</p>

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[Comment]					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[Comment]					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
[Please specify any problems]					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
[Please specify]					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
[Please specify]					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
[Please provide details]					

Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Environment & Ethics	<p>Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	<p>Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	<p>Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Environmental issues	<p>Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Ethics issues	<p>Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>					
<i>[Please provide details]</i>						
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td>1 (excellent)</td> <td>2</td> <td>3 (neutral)</td> <td>4</td> <td>5 (poor)</td> </tr> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)		

	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>										
<i>[Comment]</i>											
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>											
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td>1 (excellent)</td> <td>2</td> <td>3 (neutral)</td> <td>4</td> <td>5 (poor)</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
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<i>[Please provide details]</i>											

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.